

CASES OF HYPOFUNCTION OF THE PANCREAS IN HEPATITIS DISEASES

Togayev Azizbek Aliyor o'g'li
azizbek200794@gmail.com

Kushakova Gulhayo Bahadir qizi
gushoqovaqulhayo@gmail.com

Tashpolatov Jorabek Alisher o'g'li
toshpolatovjorabek@gmail.com

Ashurova Lobar Olimjon qizi
ashurovalobar@gmail.com

Tashkent Medical Academy Termiz branch
Assistant of the Department of Medical and Biological Chemistry

Abstract: Hypofunction of the pancreas in hepatitis diseases is as follows:

1. The functioning of the gastric gland is disturbed, the digestive system loses its condition, besides, all cells in the body begin to fight against hepatitis.
2. The activity of the pancreas is inextricably linked with the liver. The production of hormones also changes somewhat, besides, all tissues in the body are damaged by the hepatitis virus.

Key words: hepatitis, acute hepatitis, liver cirrhosis, dichlofos, chlorofos, karbofos, alcohol, liver function, chronic hepatitis.

Hepatitis (Greek: hepar; heptos - liver) is a group of diseases accompanied by inflammation of the liver. Infectious (viral hepatitis A, V, C, Ye, D) or non-infectious hepatitis. (eg, food poisoning) and primary and secondary infectious hepatitis. will be. Hepatitis. brucellosis, malaria, wounds, etc. observed in infectious diseases, as well as chronic gastrointestinal diseases. Hepatitis can also be caused by poisoning from arsenic, poisonous mushrooms, elderflower (heliotrope), poisons used in industry, agriculture and household (dichlorphos, chlorophos, karbophos, alcohol). In alcoholism, hepatitis can become severe and the liver may rot (necrosis). Hepatitis can be acute or chronic. In acute hepatitis, the whites of the eyes and the body turn yellow, the liver enlarges, heaviness and pain appear in the liver area, the patient has nausea, vomiting, loss of appetite, and drooling. Acute hepatitis sometimes occurs in toxicoses of pregnancy. If acute hepatitis is not treated in time, if the patient does not diet, the special (parenchymatous) tissue of the liver is replaced by connective tissue (see Cirrhosis of the liver). Acute hepatitis sometimes lasts for 2-3 months and turns into chronic hepatitis. At the beginning of the disease, the patient's condition almost does not change, he even continues to work, and the

disease worsens. When the whites of the eyes and the body of the patient turn yellow, even if the temperature is normal, it is necessary to put him to bed and call a doctor. If hepatitis is a consequence of poisoning, the patient should be hospitalized immediately. A patient with hepatitis should lie down and keep the area of the liver warm. The patient's food should contain enough easily digestible carbohydrates, proteins and vitamins, and should be low in fat. More wet fruit, vegetable juice, sugar, jam, honey, white bread, as well as easily digestible foods are prescribed - porridge, cottage cheese, milk, yogurt, cheese and cottage cheese (dairy foods and especially cottage cheese contain substances that protect liver cells from destruction have). Liver function recovers very slowly after the disease. To prevent chronic hepatitis, the patient must be patiently treated for a long time (sometimes up to one to two years) under the supervision of a family doctor, follow a certain routine (diet and rest).

The pancreas is a large gland in humans and animals. According to anatomical and physiological characteristics, external (exocrine) and internal (endocrine) secretion gland; secretes pancreatic juice and insulin and glucagon hormones; they go directly to the blood and control the metabolism of carbohydrates and fats; participates in digestion. The pancreas is a group of complex glands. It is second in size after the liver. It is located in the abdominal cavity, behind the stomach, near the duodenum (see Intestine), transversely opposite the lumbar vertebrae. Its length is 12-18 cm, its weight is about 70-80 g, the capsule of the gland is very thin. Glandular cells secrete gastric secretions. The excretory ducts of the pancreas enlarge and join together and flow into the cephalic excretory duct, which goes along the gland and opens into the duodenum along with the common bile duct. Pancreas b. Pancreatitis, tumor formation, and diabetes are observed when insulin production is disturbed. The "jaundice period" of the disease also takes place in its own way. With the yellowing of the whites of the eyes, the peak period of V. g. begins; As soon as the patient turns yellow in form A, his condition becomes much lighter and he recovers. In V. g. transmitted by parenteral route, compared to those transmitted by mouth, the period of jaundice is longer, the patient does not recover quickly, the medicine dries up, nausea, in some cases the body itches (cholestatic type). Depending on the stage of V. g., its clinical symptoms can be manifested in different ways: in the non-jaundic form, the patient does not turn yellow, the color of his urine and feces does not change, and the amount of bilirubin in the blood is normal. The patient's eyes turn yellow for a short time, and the amount of bilirubin quickly returns to its original value. In the subclinical form, clinical signs are almost not observed, only the lip. can be known from the tests. The form of viral transmission of V. g. is more complex, it passes in secret and gradually takes on a chronic character. The chronic form of the disease can cause severe complications (acute hepatic encephalopathy, hemorrhagic, edema-ascites syndrome, etc.).

References: R. Sobirova Biochemistry 2021, Wikipedia,

R. Sobirova Biochemistry 2021 Part II.